

DIFFUSION PLAN CREATED FOR THE PROJECT:

Structure-function studies of Type VI secretion system toxins (T6SS-TOXINS)

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1. Introduction

To ensure strategic planning and effective management of communication and dissemination activities and tools from the beginning, this DIFUSSION PLAN is prepared and made available to the members and collaborators of the T6SS-TOXINS project.

This project has requested funding from the Ministry of Science and Innovation, within the framework of the State Program to Promote Scientific-Technical Research and its Transfer, of the State Plan for Scientific, Technical and Innovation Research 2021-2023 (hereinafter State Plan). Therefore, this COMMUNICATION PLAN considers "Article 19. Obligations of the beneficiary entities" of the Order approving the call for applications for the year 2021 of the procedure for granting aid to "Knowledge Generation Projects".

Specifically, the DIFFUSION PLAN considers the following points of Article 19. Obligations of the beneficiary entities:

2. When the results are not susceptible to the protection of industrial or intellectual property rights, the scientific publications resulting from the funding granted under this call must be available in open access, per article 37 of Law 14 / 2011, of June 1.

To this end, the authors of scientific papers that have been accepted for publication in serial or periodical publications may choose to publish in open access journals or self-archive in institutional or open access thematic repositories, collected on the RECOLECTA platform of the Foundation. Española de Ciencia y Tecnología (FECYT), or in other repositories promoted by the institutions themselves.

The publication will take place within a period not exceeding six months after its commercial publication, except in the area of Social Sciences and Humanities, where the established period will not exceed one year.

Research data must be deposited in institutional, national and/or international repositories within two years from the end of the project to promote access to research data from funded grants.

3. The beneficiary entities must comply with the provisions on communication and visibility established in annexe IX and Article 50 of Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 of Common Provisions and report the funds received in publications, other research results, lectures, inventoried equipment and activities.

Reference to any of the projects that are the subject of these grants in any means of dissemination must include that it has been financed by the Ministry of Science and Innovation, the State Research Agency, and the ERDF. If there are space limitations, particularly in publications, it will be mentioned as indicated in article 9.3.a) (PROJECT REFERENCE Project funded by MCIN / AEI / 10.13039 / 501100011033 / FEDER, EU).

This Communication and Dissemination Plan is made up of the following elements:

- Objectives and target groups.
- Strategy and content of advertising measures
- Indicative budget for the application of the planned measures.
- Indication of the expected results of the advertising and dissemination measures.
- Formal requirements and legal obligations.

2. objectives

The general objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Plan of the T6SS-TOXINS Project are the following:

- Optimize the flow of information between members and collaborators of the project and organize efficient communication between the institutions participating in the project.
- Make the Project known to potential stakeholders and the primary beneficiaries.
- Inform and communicate the results to public and private organizations and entities of other European regions and national and European institutions interested in the project.

The specific objectives of internal communication are:

- C1. Systematize communication between collaborators, members, and the project leader since the correct management and execution of the project will depend on it.
- C2. Keep the collaborators informed on administrative obligations, as well as monitoring and evaluation.

The specific objectives of the dissemination and external communication activities are:

- D1. Advertise the project to the target audience: what it consists of; its objectives; reason for its creation; formation of the partnership; results; etc.
- D2. Disseminate the progress made and the results obtained in the course of the project.
- D3. Provide a documentary base and reference material for future work or studies
- D4. Disseminate new knowledge or reference material for policymakers at local, regional, national and European levels. For instance, assistance to workshops on antimicrobial resistance (AMR) for public health officials or policy briefs
- D5. Carry out effective, transparent and understandable communication to the entire society on the project's issues.

3. Messages

The project messages summarize the "essence" of the project. Being concrete and straightforward, they form the basis for all outreach activities, and they must be relevant to target audiences. The messages will remind you of the objectives and highlight the added value and benefits the project will bring.

The following are examples of key messages for the dissemination and external communication actions.

Aspect to spread	Message	Example of specific activity or result
Transnational cooperation aims to advance our knowledge about the virulence of <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	"Partners from Spain and the United Kingdom join forces to understand the virulence of <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> "	Message for the Website

Discovery of the mechanisms of action of toxins produced by <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	"Fundamental science is the foundation of innovation in our society / companies"	Message in Press Release and publication in scientific journals
Discovery of the atomic structure of toxins produced by <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	"Structural information can lead to the development of new strategies to fight antimicrobial resistance"	Message for conferences and website

4. Recipients

The communication and dissemination activities of the T6SS-TOXINS Project aim to convey a series of messages and information to identified target groups. These are the following groups:

Direct internal recipients:

- The collaborators (the partnership).
- Responsible for management and coordination of the State Plan (State Research Agency (AEI))

External direct recipients:

- Companies from the participating regions, especially
 - Pharmaceutical companies
 - Small and Medium-size Enterprises (SMEs) with innovation needs.
 - SMEs from mature sectors in need of innovation or diversification.
 - Young innovative and/or technology-based companies.
- Entrepreneurs with business projects in the pre-incubation, incubation or business creation phase.
- Potential entrepreneurs: students in the last years of technological careers, doctoral students, Vocational Training students and other people with initiative or business ideas.
- Intermediate organizations, such as technology centres, universities, etc. and entities that support companies interested in innovation.

General recipients:

- Public bodies and entities in Europe and the United Kingdom.
- Political decision-makers at local, regional, national and European levels.
- The media and economic and social agents, other interest groups.
- Society in general.

5. Strategy and Activities

The various actions and materials prepared for their dissemination will be grouped into three lines of action depending on the target group:

1. Internal Communication: Among the project collaborators. It includes the dissemination of the midterm and final evaluation reports of the project.
2. External Communication: With direct recipients and potential beneficiaries of the project results.
3. General Dissemination: Political stakeholders and society will be informed through the publication in the press of information related to the project.

These three lines of action that form the pillars of the communication and dissemination strategy foresee the coherent adaptation of the activities and communication tools to the different objectives and target groups. The relationship between objectives, target groups and activities/tools is therefore as follows:

Recipients	Direct internal recipients	External direct recipients		General recipients		
		(collaborators, AEI)	(scientific community)	(Companies, entrepreneurs)	Political Decision-makers	Media
objectives	(collaborators, AEI)	(scientific community)	(Companies, entrepreneurs)	Political Decision-makers	Media	Society
C1. Systematized communication	Web Page, Web Tools, Reports, Exercise					
C2. Fluid information	Meetings, Telecommunication tools					
D1. Publicize the Project		Website	Website	Website	Website	Website, Tweets
D2. Give to know results		Website, Publications in scientific journals, National and international scientific congresses	Website, Business, professional or sector magazines	Website, Press releases	Website, Press releases	Website, Press releases, Tweets
D3. Working reference material		Data available in freely accessible repositories	Press publications, Seminars	Press publications, Website		
D4. New knowledge as a basis for political decision				Publications, Website		
D5. Transparent communication on project topic					Press Notes	Notes Press, Events

5.1 Internal communication

The objective of the Internal Communication strategy is to systematize and structure the information in a way that guarantees effective and transparent management of the project, as well as to ensure fluid and efficient communication between those directly involved, that is, the project members, collaborators, and the State Investigation Agency. This internal communication is intended to be achieved through the use of the following tools:

- Prepare and share Activity Reports
- Intranet enabled on the project website with the following management and information exchange tools:

- Enabled and secure access for each partner
- Document sharing - document upload and download possible
- Access to updated planning and management documents (Work Plan, Task Distribution, Collaboration Agreement, Report Templates, Press Release Models, Corporate Image Manual)
- Library with documents and useful links for the work of the partners.
- Regular Management meetings.
- Telecommunication tools (telephone, email, videoconference, messaging).

5.2 Image, External Communication and Diffusion

The external communication and dissemination strategy include both dissemination and communication to potential direct beneficiaries and indirect target groups (e.g., microbiology or structural biology communities, decision-makers, other European regions, the media and society).

The strategy aimed at direct beneficiaries and other general recipients includes the following lines of action and dissemination tools:

- Corporate image
 - Creation of a Logo and a Corporate Image
- Web and Information Technologies
 - Project's website
 - Pages about T6SS-TOXINS in the Sites of each collaborator
 - Participation in social networks
- Promotional material:
 - Cover letters and invitations to people in business and entrepreneurs
- Work with the media:
 - Press releases
 - Articles
 - Introduction of news on the project website
- Acts and Events:
 - Social awareness days (2 during the project)
 - Roundtables (2 each year)
 - National scientific conferences (1 per year; e.g., [Congress of the Spanish Biophysical Society](#), or [Congreso de la Sociedad Española de Bioquímica y Biología Molecular](#))
 - International scientific conferences (1 per year; e.g., [Gordon Research Conference on Microbial Toxins and Pathogenicity](#), or [European Workshop on Bacterial Protein Toxins](#))
- Publications and Reference Material:
 - Publication of a DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
 - Publication of the results in international scientific journals (e.g., [Nature Communications](#), [Journal of Bacteriology](#))
 - Deposit experimental data in free access repositories according to the DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN.

The next chapter presents in more detail the key tools in communication and dissemination strategies.

5.3 Head of Project Communication

The project appoints David Albesa-Jové – Principal Investigator – Head of Communication.

As the person in charge of communication, he must ensure the proper development of this Plan and control that all the activities included in the project are carried out successfully. In addition, he will help coordinate the different communication activities of the partnership.

6. Tools

The essential tools and elements for dissemination and communication are as follows:

The project website will be a central element that serves to offer direct information and as a tool for disseminating and sending other materials, such as, for example, reference material, publications, and the logo. Likewise, the website may be used to invite to acts and events. Second, but not least, it fulfils - through a secure intranet with restricted access to project members and collaborators - the function of internal communication between partners. The creation of the website is the responsibility of the Project Communication Manager, who will be in charge of its management and updating, placing it on the entity's servers. In addition,

Working with the media is another essential element. The disseminated press releases and articles must be adapted to the language of the media, using headlines, subtitles, organizing the information according to its importance, using visual tools (graphics, photographs, etc.) and offering data to try to Attract attention. The language must be clear and direct. Short sentences that provide relevant and understandable information. If possible, it is recommended to speak directly with the journalist to ensure that the story will appear in the media. Meetings, working groups, workshops or seminars are good opportunities to hold a press conference or a public presentation of the project in the media. It is always recommended to indicate the project website and a contact person and address. It is also

limitations, particularly in publications, it will be mentioned as indicated as follows: PROJECT REFERENCE Project funded by MCIN / AEI / 10.13039 / 501100011033 / FEDER, EU.

All the materials produced in paper format (reports, bulletins, associated documentation) or in electronic format (CD / DVD-ROM, Power-Point presentations, webpage...) must contain the following logos to inform of the actions carried out by the Ministry of Science and Innovation and the State Research Agency and by the ERDF:

- The Ministry of Science and Innovation and the State Research Agency logo: this logo must be used following the provisions of its User Manual. it is possible to download the logo at the following link:

<http://www.aei.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.26172fcf4eb029fa6ec7da6901432ea0/?vgnnextoid=81c4d66f36af9510VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD>.

- The European emblem. The material produced must also respect the graphic specifications established by the Commission. Under the emblem of the European Union, it is necessary to indicate "European Union" and the Fund that finances the Project, ERDF. EU emblem can be downloaded at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/publications/guidelines/2015/example-of-logos

When using it, it is recommended that both logos appear at the same size on the first page of the documents produced.

Failure to comply with the regulations on information and advertising may lead to the ineligibility of the expenses inherent to the documents/dissemination material produced, and the financial corrections established by the European Commission Regulation (EC) No. 1828/2006.

Frequent mistakes in the use of logos and emblems that should be avoided are:

- At different heights and sizes.
- Absence of the mention relative to the European Union and the Fund.
- Partial overlap of one logo by another.
- Wrong Program logo.
- Incorrect insertion of the reference to the European Union and the Fund.
- Absence of the European emblem or the Ministry of Science and Innovation and the State Research Agency logo.

On project webpages, the logos mentioned above must appear at least on the home page. In addition, it is also recommended to include links to the page of the State Research Agency, other websites of the European Commission and the websites of the beneficiary institutions.